

Original Research

Macroeconomic Factors and Tax Revenue Performance in South Africa: A Markov-Switching Model Approach

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Abstract

Tax revenue is a key funding source for South Africa's government, essential for public services. However, it has been volatile in recent years. This study examines the macroeconomic factors influencing tax revenue performance in South Africa from 2000Q1 to 2023Q3, utilizing the Markov Switching Model (MSM). The results show that macroeconomic factors operate differently under varying economic conditions. Specifically, inflation and interest rates negatively impact tax revenue in regime 1, while they positively influence it in regime 2. In contrast, the exchange rate and current account balance positively affect tax revenue in regime 1 but negatively in regime 2. Economic growth consistently has a positive effect in both regimes. Overall, the findings highlight the need to consider economic conditions when evaluating tax revenue performance. Policymakers must account for these differing effects to develop effective tax policies that optimize revenue collection in South Africa. Understanding how various economic conditions influence tax revenue enables authorities to adjust their strategies for sustainable and consistent revenue generation.

Keywords: Macroeconomic Factors, Markov-Switching Model, Tax Revenue.

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Introduction

Markov-switching models are essential tools for analyzing processes that experience infrequent, discrete transitions over time. Introduced by Hamilton (1989), they have become popular nonlinear time series models. These models are widely applied in sectors like finance and economics. In South Africa, a Markov-switching model can capture shifts and fluctuations in macroeconomic factors affecting tax collection. Gökpnar (2023) argues that any factor influencing income, wealth, or expenditures that generate tax revenue reduces it immediately. These factors interact significantly, especially concerning macroeconomic conditions. By recognizing these shifts, policymakers and economists in South Africa can better understand tax revenue dynamics, enabling more informed fiscal policy decisions. During economic downturns or recessions, a Markov-switching model could identify periods when tax revenue likely declines due to decreased consumer spending and lower business profits. Conversely, it could also highlight phases of economic growth when tax revenue may increase, driven by rising employment rates and heightened economic activity. In recent years, the South African economy has underperformed, leading to declining tax revenue amidst challenges such as high unemployment rates, slow economic growth, and political instability. These factors have strained the government's ability to fund social programs and essential services, resulting in budget deficits and increasing debt levels. Poor tax revenue performance has been cited as a significant contributor to substantial budget deficits in emerging economies (Chaudhry & Munir 2010), and South Africa is no exception. Over the past decade, tax collections have shown significant deficits, leading to increased government borrowing and debt. Additionally, reliance on borrowing to cover budget deficits raises concerns about the country's long-term financial stability. Enhancing tax revenue is critical for managing potential economic, health, and financial shocks, as well as for delivering public services (Gnangnon and Jean-François, 2017). As tax collection improves, the government can allocate more resources to public development projects, enhance health and education facilities, and ultimately improve the quality of life for its citizens (Streimikiene et al. 2018).

There have been varying results in research on the factors affecting tax revenue. For example, Đurović et al. (2024) identified a negative correlation between tax revenue and inflation among the Visegrad Group nations (the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia) using panel data estimates. In contrast, Belullo and Dužman (2011) employed DMOLS to reveal a significant correlation between GDP and government revenue. Similarly, Ikpesu (2022) found that the exchange rate, GDP, foreign direct investment (FDI), and inflation all impact Nigeria's tax revenue. Atolagbe and Abiodun (2021) analyzed trade liberalization and concluded that it increases tax revenues in Nigeria, using an ARDL approach. Mmbulaheni et al. (2024) utilized an error correction model and found that trade openness, FDI, and GDP per capita are statistically significant and positively correlated with tax revenue performance in South Africa. In another study, Hlongwane et al. (2022) found that government expenditure promotes growth, while trade and inflation negatively affect taxes in both the short and long term in South Africa. They noted that GDP has a short-term positive influence on taxes but does not show significant long-term effects.

These studies highlight the importance of economic factors in shaping tax revenue performance across countries. However, they often overlook potential non-linear effects and switching behavior, assuming a linear relationship between these factors and tax revenue. We argue that non-linear effects and switching behavior should be considered, as the macroeconomic factors influencing tax revenue performance in South Africa may not follow a linear trajectory. For instance, during an economic expansion (regime one), rising incomes may increase tax revenues by boosting consumer spending. Conversely, high inflation rates during a recession (regime two) could hinder tax revenue by deterring investment and reducing consumer spending. By incorporating these non-linear effects and switching behaviors, we can achieve a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between macroeconomic variables and tax revenue performance, leading to more effective policy recommendations for enhancing tax collection in South Africa.

A research question examines whether changes in macroeconomic factors significantly affect tax revenue performance in South Africa and whether the effects vary during economic expansions and recessions. The study employs a Markov Switching Model (MSM) to investigate the relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue performance across two regimes. The findings indicate that macroeconomic parameters respond differently during these periods, leading to variations in tax revenue. This suggests that policymakers should consider the changing economic landscape when formulating tax policies to optimize revenue generation.

Following the introduction, Section 2 presents a literature review. Section 3 outlines the research methodology, data, theoretical development of the variables, and model. Section 4 interprets empirical findings. In Section 5, the results are discussed, while Section 6 concludes the paper with policy recommendations.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The Theory of Optimal Taxation

The traditional theory of optimal taxation suggests that the tax system should minimize economic distortions while maximizing social welfare (Ramsey, 1927). Frank Ramsey developed this theory, which has been refined by others. Key objectives include efficiency, equality, simplicity, and addressing trade-offs and practical limitations. Notable contributors, such as Saez (2002) and Diamond and Mirrlees (1971), expanded on Ramsey's concepts to address contemporary challenges. A core principle is the "tax schedule," which determines tax rates at various income levels to balance efficiency and equality. By adjusting tax rates according to income levels, policymakers can promote economic growth while ensuring a fair distribution of tax burdens. Higher tax rates on the wealthy can help reduce income inequality, while lower tax rates on lower-income individuals can encourage spending and stimulate economic activity.

South Africa faces significant challenges, including high-income inequality, unemployment, and fiscal deficits (see Simkins 2004; Marire, 2022). These issues impact the country's application of optimum taxation theory, specifically in achieving a balance

between equity and efficiency. The income tax system in South Africa incorporates vertical equity by imposing higher rates on individuals with higher incomes. This approach seeks to reduce inequality, but it is important to avoid excessively high rates that may discourage productivity and investment.

The Laffer Curve Theory

The theory examines the relationship between tax rates and tax collections, named after economist Arthur Laffer (Fedeli et al., 2024). Laffer (2004) posits that there is a tax rate that maximizes tax revenue. At very low tax rates, the government may struggle to generate enough revenue to fund its services. Reduced tax rates can increase taxpayers' disposable income, boosting consumer demand and economic activity. According to Amadeo (2021), this surge in economic activity can expand the tax base, offsetting revenue lost from tax cuts. Conversely, at extremely high tax rates, economic activity may decline, leading to lower revenue due to tax evasion, defined as the unlawful withholding of taxes owed (Quentin, 2014). Ultimately, finding the optimal balance in tax rates is crucial for the government to finance its services while promoting economic growth. Figure 1 below illustrates the Laffer curve.

Figure 1. General form of a Laffer Curve.

Source (Laffer, 2004)

Figure 1 illustrates the relationship between tax rates and revenue through the Laffer Curve, suggesting that there exists an optimal tax rate that maximizes revenue. This concept can be understood by examining South Africa's tax policy. The primary sources of revenue for South Africa include value-added tax (VAT), corporate income tax (CIT), and personal income tax (PIT) (Pamba, 2022). The country's low personal income and corporate tax rates may hinder tax collection, preventing the government from fulfilling its expenditure obligations for essential public services such as healthcare, education, and infrastructure. South Africa's revenue-raising potential is maximized at a moderate tax rate, which encourages compliance among individuals and corporations due to the lower tax burden, leading to significant government income. Conversely, excessively high tax rates may incentivize tax avoidance or the relocation of assets outside the country. The

Laffer Curve is particularly relevant in South Africa when discussing tax policy changes in the context of substantial income inequality. During 1960 to 2007, Schoeman and Van Heerden (2009) examined optimal tax strategies to enable the South African economy to reach its maximum potential. They concluded that to enhance economic growth, authorities should consider modifying tax policy, as the actual average tax burden exceeds the optimal level. According to their model, the optimal tax-to-GDP ratio for the South African economy is 18.5%. This is in line with Scully's (2000) findings that the optimal tax rate for the United States is 19%, while that for New Zealand is 23%.

Empirical Literature Review

Durović et al. (2024) examined the factors influencing tax revenue in the Visegrad Group nations from 1994 to 2023 using panel data. The findings indicated that the Pooled Mean Group (PMG) model significantly affected delayed tax revenue. A 1% increase in GDP and population led to short-term changes in tax revenue, while tax income declined with increasing inflation rates. The EU expansion had an impact on both long-term and short-term tax revenues. Furthermore, increases in government revenue positively affected tax revenues in the long run, while long-term unemployment had a more significant effect.

Using data from 1981 to 2019, Atolagbe and Abiodun (2021) examine the impact of trade liberalization on Nigeria's tax revenue. They employed the Error Correction Model (ECM) and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique to forecast total and domestic tax revenue. Tax revenue increased by 3% for every unit rise in trade liberalization. The study found a significant correlation between macroeconomic indicators and tax revenue, including mining and petroleum, agriculture, foreign direct investment, per capita income, exchange rate, and inflation rate.

The Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) method was employed by Ikpesu (2022) to analyze data from 1981 to 2021 to determine the factors influencing tax income in Nigeria. The regression estimations identified the key macroeconomic factors affecting Nigeria's tax revenue as the annual GDP growth rate, foreign debt, FDI, foreign aid, inflation, and the currency exchange rate.

Piancastelli and Thirlwall (2020) conducted a study using panel data from 59 developed and developing nations from 1995 to 2015. In contrast, Boukbech et al. (2018) performed a panel analysis of 29 lower-middle-income countries from 2001 to 2014. Both studies found that factors such as public expenditure, population size, per capita GDP, inflation, the level of openness, and the GDP share of agriculture and services significantly influence the tax revenue-to-GDP ratio.

Okonkwo (2018) used the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) approach to study the factors influencing taxes in Nigeria from 1980 to 2014. The study found that the primary factors influencing taxes were inflation, money supply, interest rates, and income.

Ethiopian tax revenue from 1975 to 2013 was examined by Ayenew (2016). The study concluded that GDP growth, manufacturing, and foreign aid positively affect tax income, while inflation negatively affects it.

Using an imbalanced panel dataset of 39 nations, Addison and Levin (2012) identified the factors influencing tax revenue in sub-Saharan Africa from 1980 to 2005. The report highlights several variables affecting tax revenue, including the tax base, structural issues, foreign aid, and conflict.

From 2000 to 2010, Belullo and Dužman (2011) examined the connection between Croatia's GDP and government revenue. They found a strong Granger correlation between changes in government revenue and GDP.

Using time series data from 1990 to 2018, Mmbulaheni et al. (2024) examine factors influencing tax revenue performance in South Africa. They identify both long- and short-term dynamics among the variables using Johansen's cointegration and error correction models. The findings indicate that trade openness, foreign direct investment (FDI), and GDP per capita are statistically significant and positively correlated with tax revenue performance. The relationship between inflation and tax revenue performance is statistically significant but inverse, while the relationship between unemployment and tax revenue performance is statistically significant and inverse.

Hlongwane et al. (2022) use the ARDL model to investigate factors influencing taxation in South Africa from 1972 to 2021. Their findings show that government expenditure is a significant positive predictor of taxes in both the short and long term. In contrast, inflation and inflationary pressures are significant negative factors. While economic growth is a significant positive predictor of taxes in the short term, it becomes a statistically insignificant negative determinant in the long term.

Gaps in Existing Literature

In the existing literature, insufficient exploration exists regarding the impact of macroeconomic factors on tax revenue using nonlinear and regime-switching models. This knowledge gap hinders our understanding of how these factors influence tax revenue under different economic conditions. Nonlinear and regime-switching models provide a nuanced framework for capturing the complex relationships between macroeconomic variables and tax revenue. By utilizing these methodologies, researchers can provide deeper insights into how tax revenue responds to economic regime shifts, thereby enhancing the tools available to policymakers and analysts. This approach improves prediction accuracy and supports the development of more effective fiscal policies tailored to diverse economic scenarios.

Research Hypothesis

H₁: Macroeconomic factors, such as inflation, interest rate, exchange rate, GDP growth, and current account balance have a significant and regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance in South Africa.

H₂: The relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue performance differs between periods of economic expansion and recession.

Methodology

Data Collection

The study utilized secondary time series data obtained from three institutions: the South African Reserve Bank (SARB), the World Bank, and the International Monetary Fund (IMF). The SARB is a primary source of data on the South African economy, providing statistics on tax revenue, inflation, interest rates, and exchange rates (Website: <https://www.resbank.co.za>, Data Access: SARB Statistics). The World Bank offers data on real GDP growth (Website: <https://www.worldbank.org>, Data Access: World Development Indicators), while the IMF provides information on current account balances (Website: <https://www.imf.org>, Data Access: IMF Data). Data were collected from the first quarter of 2000 (2000Q1) to the third quarter of 2023 (2023Q3). All variables were extracted from publicly available economic and financial datasets. EViews' frequency conversion tool was employed when quarterly data were unavailable from the World Bank, following the methodology of Mamvura and Sibanda (2020).

Theoretical development of variables

Dependent Variable

Tax revenue (TR) performance serves as the dependent variable in this study, measured by the percentage of GDP (see Queku et al., 2024). This variable is derived from all taxes in South Africa and is essential for assessing the government's capacity to finance public services and infrastructure development (see Mohammed and Tangl, 2024). By examining the macroeconomic factors that influence tax revenue performance, policymakers can make informed decisions to enhance revenue collection and foster economic growth in the country.

Independent variables

The consumer price index (CPI) measures inflation (INF) by reflecting the quarterly percentage change in the average cost incurred by consumers for a basket of goods and services (see Anware, 2014). This cost may remain fixed or fluctuate at predetermined intervals, such as annually (Velaj and Prendi, 2014). In South Africa, inflation can significantly affect tax revenue by increasing the prices of goods and services, which may reduce consumer spending and lower government tax revenues. Mmbulaheni et al. (2024) found a negative link between inflation and tax revenue performance in South Africa. This study also anticipated that inflation would negatively affect tax revenue performance in South Africa under both regimes.

Interest rates (IR) have a significant impact on tax revenue performance (Chamisa and Sunde, 2024). High interest rates increase borrowing costs for businesses and consumers, leading to reduced economic activity and lower tax revenue (Kozlov, 2023). On the other hand, low interest rates make borrowing more affordable, promoting investment and consumption, thereby potentially enhancing tax revenue. Therefore, the connection between interest rates and tax revenue is expected to be influenced by prevailing economic conditions. For example, during economic recessions, reducing interest rates

may not have a significant impact on tax revenue compared to periods of economic growth.

Exchange rate (EXR) fluctuations can have a significant impact on tax revenue performance in South Africa. When the exchange rate weakens, exports become more competitive, leading to increased economic activity and higher tax revenue (Masiya et al., 2015). On the other hand, a stronger exchange rate can reduce tax revenue by making exports more expensive, potentially hindering economic growth (Masiya et al., 2015). The relationship between exchange rates and tax revenue is expected to vary depending on economic conditions. During economic downturns, a weak exchange rate may not boost tax revenue as overall demand for goods and services remains low. However, during periods of economic growth, a stronger exchange rate may still result in higher tax revenue as businesses might be able to absorb the increased costs associated with exporting.

Real GDP (RGDP) growth influences tax revenue performance in South Africa (Pamba, 2022; Mmbulaheni et al., 2024). When the economy grows, businesses report higher profits, and individuals earn increased incomes, resulting in a boost in tax revenue (see Cigdem and Altaylar, 2021). Mmbulaheni et al. (2024) found a positive relationship between RGDP and tax revenue performance in South Africa. This study expects that real GDP growth will have a varying effect on tax revenue performance under two economic conditions. For instance, during strong economic expansion, South Africa experienced a significant rise in tax revenue due to elevated corporate profits and personal income. In contrast, during economic downturns, tax revenue declined as businesses incurred losses and individuals faced job losses.

Current account balances (CAB) play a vital role in determining tax revenue performance. Studies by Abiad et al. (2009) and Abbas et al. (2011) have analyzed how fiscal policy, including tax policies, interacts with current account balances. When a country experiences a deficit in its current account balance, it may struggle to generate enough tax revenue to meet its financial obligations (see Abbas et al. 2011). This can lead to budget deficits and the need for additional borrowing, which further strains the economy. The impact of the current account balance on tax revenue performance in South Africa is expected to vary with economic conditions. For instance, during periods of economic growth, a deficit in the current account balance may not significantly affect tax revenue as it would during a recession.

Unit Root Tests

Before estimating the relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue, it is essential to assess whether the variables are stationary or possess unit roots. A time series with a unit root indicates non-stationarity, which can lead to spurious results when using standard regression techniques.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test (1981)

The ADF test determines whether a time series contains a unit root. The null hypothesis states that the series is non-stationary due to a unit root, while the alternative hypothesis suggests that the series is stationary.

The ADF test equation is:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^p \delta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where:

- Y_t is the time series (e.g., tax revenue or a macroeconomic factor),
- $\Delta Y_t = Y_t - Y_{t-1}$ is the first difference of the series,
- α is a constant (drift term),
- βt represents the trend in the series,
- γ is the coefficient of the lagged level of the series, which is critical for testing the unit root (if $\gamma = 0$, there is a unit root),
- δ_i are the coefficients of the lagged differences to account for autocorrelation,
- ϵ_t is the error term.

The decision rule is:

- The null hypothesis should be rejected (the series is stationary) if the test statistic is less than the critical value.
- Reject the null hypothesis if the test statistic exceeds the critical value (there is a unit root in the series).

Phillips-Perron (PP) Test (1988)

The Phillips-Perron (PP) test is an alternative method for testing unit roots. It adjusts for serial correlation and heteroscedasticity in the error terms without including lagged difference terms. While the PP test equation resembles that of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, it includes a non-parametric correction to address potential data issues.

The PP test is based on the following regression:

$$Y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma Y_{t-1} + \epsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where:

- Y_t is the time series,
- α is the constant,
- βt is the deterministic trend,
- γ is the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable,
- ϵ_t is the error term.

In contrast to the ADF test, the PP test does not account for serial correlations by incorporating lagged differences in the dependent variable. The residuals of the test are adjusted for serial correlation using this method.

As with the ADF test, the PP test follows the same decision rule:

- The null hypothesis is rejected if the test statistic is less than the critical value, indicating stationarity.
- The null hypothesis cannot be rejected if the test statistic is greater than the critical value, indicating the presence of a unit root.

Markov Switching Model (MSM)

In econometrics, Goldfeld and Quandt introduced the Markov-Switching Model (MSM) in 1973. Hamilton's 1989 analysis of business cycle dynamics further popularized this method. Markov-Switching models capture regime changes in a time series by allowing parameters to transition between multiple states. When applied to tax revenue performance in South Africa, an MSM model analyzes how macroeconomic factors such as inflation, real GDP, interest rates, exchange rates, and current account balances influence tax revenue under varying economic conditions, including expansionary and recessionary periods. Policymakers and economists can integrate Markov-Switching models into their assessments to gain insights into how different economic conditions affect tax revenue collection. This approach fosters a more nuanced understanding of the relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue, potentially leading to more effective fiscal policy decisions.

Consider a time series of tax revenue, Y_t influenced by macroeconomic factors, X_t , including inflation, RGDP, interest rates, exchange rates, and the current account balance. The relationship between tax revenue and these factors can vary across different regimes, such as high-growth periods (state 1) and low-growth periods (state 2). Transitions between these states are governed by a Markov process.

General Model:

$$Y_t = \beta_{S_t} X_t + \epsilon_t \quad (3)$$

Where:

- Y_t is the tax revenue at time t
- X_t is a vector of macroeconomic factors (e.g., like inflation, interest rates, exchange rate, RGDP and current account balance)
- β_{S_t} is a state-dependent coefficient (varying with regime S_t),
- ϵ_t is an error term (usually assumed to be normally distributed),
- First-order Markov processes determine the unobserved (latent) state variable, S_t .

Markov Process:

Markov processes with transition probabilities evolve the state variable S_t :

$$P = (S_t = j | S_{t-1} = i) = p_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Where:

- p_{ij} is the probability of switching from state i to state j ,
- i and $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$, with k being the number of states (regimes).

Transition Probability Matrix:

As a matrix of transition probabilities, P can be expressed as follows:

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} \end{pmatrix}$$

In this equation, p_{ij} represents the probability of switching between regimes i and j

State-Specific Equations

The equation might be as follows in regime 1 (e.g., expansionary period):

$$Y_t^{(1)} = \beta_1 X_t + \epsilon_t^{(1)} \quad (5)$$

The equation might be as follows in regime 2 (e.g., recessionary period):

$$Y_t^{(2)} = \beta_1 X_t + \epsilon_t^{(2)} \quad (6)$$

Estimation

The parameters of the MS model (i.e., β_1, β_2, p_{ij}) are estimated using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE). To construct the likelihood function, we use the joint distribution of Y_t and the unobserved state S_t , assuming that X_t is a macroeconomic factor.

Example:

Let Y_t be the tax revenue, and X_t include inflation, interest rates, exchange rate, RGDP and current account balance. Then, the Markov-Switching model could look like:

For Regime 1:

$$Y_t = \beta_0^{(1)} + \beta_1^{(1)} INF_t + \beta_2^{(1)} IR_t + \beta_3^{(1)} EXR_t + \beta_4^{(1)} RGDP_t + \beta_5^{(1)} CAB_t + \epsilon_t^1 \quad (7)$$

if $S_t = 1$

For Regime 2:

$$Y_t = \beta_0^{(2)} + \beta_1^{(2)} INF_t + \beta_2^{(2)} IR_t + \beta_3^{(2)} EXR_t + \beta_4^{(2)} RGDP_t + \beta_5^{(2)} CAB_t + \epsilon_t^2 \quad (8)$$

if $S_t = 2$

Where the parameters $\beta_0^{(1)} + \beta_1^{(1)}$, etc., differ across regimes.

According to this model, tax revenue is influenced by macroeconomic factors that vary based on whether the economy is experiencing high or low growth. The Markov-switching process effectively captures these transitions in the economic environment.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics for various macroeconomic factors related to tax revenue. The mean tax revenue (TR) is 10.07895, the mean inflation risk is 112.4117, the mean interest rate (IR) is 10.80063, and the mean exchange rate risk (EXR) is 85.84947. The mean economic growth (RGDP) is 2.336842, and the mean current account balance (CAB) is -2.060138. The high mean inflation risk indicates a significant level of inflation that could impact tax revenue. The negative mean current account balance suggests that South Africa may be experiencing a deficit, potentially influencing tax revenue as well.

Tax revenue has a standard deviation of 12.03482, inflation risk has one of 37.16027, and interest rates have one of 2.558710. The exchange rate risk is 11.95657, and the current account balance is 2.778180. These statistics provide insights into the volatility of key macroeconomic factors affecting tax revenue in South Africa. The standard deviation of tax revenue indicates a moderate degree of fluctuation. In contrast, inflation risk and exchange rate risk display higher variability. Interest rates show a low and stable standard deviation, suggesting a consistent influence on tax revenue. Additionally, the current account balance reflects a moderate level of variation, highlighting potential impacts on tax revenue from international trade and investment.

Table 1. A Summary of Descriptive Statistics

Description	TR	INF	IR	EXR	RGDP	CAB
Mean	10.07895	112.4117	10.80063	85.84947	2.336842	-2.060138
Median	9.500000	107.2600	10.25000	83.04000	2.500000	-2.805575
Maximum	77.90000	174.9900	17.00000	108.9900	5.600000	4.123380
Minimum	-35.40000	58.14000	7.000000	64.68000	-6.300000	-5.836930
Std. Deviation	12.03482	37.16027	2.558710	11.95657	2.169521	2.778180
Skewness	1.485138	0.211790	0.659412	0.269724	-1.188351	0.564215
Kurtosis	15.18447	1.624717	2.626748	1.831482	5.689875	2.250728
Jarque-Bera (JB)	622.5821	8.197014	7.436177	6.556740	50.99974	7.262601
Probability	0.000000	0.016597	0.024280	0.037690	0.000000	0.026482
Observations	95	95	95	95	95	95

Skewness results for tax revenue in South Africa show values of 1.485138 for tax revenue, 0.211790 for inflation risk, 0.659412 for interest rate, 0.269724 for exchange rate risk, -1.188351 for RGDP, and 0.564215 for the current account balance. These statistics indicate that tax revenue is positively skewed, suggesting outliers are pulling the distribution to the right. Inflation risk and exchange rate risk are relatively low compared to interest rate risk and the current account balance. The negative skewness of RGDP

indicates potential periods of economic contraction affecting tax revenue. Overall, these statistics provide insight into the macroeconomic factors influencing tax revenue in South Africa.

Kurtosis results for South Africa show tax revenue at 15.18447, inflation risk at 1.624717, interest rate risk at 2.626748, exchange rate risk at 1.831482, RGDP at 5.689875, and the current account balance at 2.250728. The kurtosis value of 15.18447 indicates a high degree of tail risk for tax revenue. In contrast, inflation and exchange rate risks have lower tail risks with kurtosis values of 1.624717 and 1.831482, respectively. Interest rate risk is intermediate, with a kurtosis value of 2.626748. The positive kurtosis values for RGDP and the current account balance suggest these variables are positively skewed, indicating that higher values are more likely than lower values.

Unit root test

The unit root test is a statistical method for determining whether a time series is stationary or non-stationary. When applied to tax revenue performance in South Africa, this test can uncover long-term trends or patterns in the data that may influence the model's accuracy.

Table 2. ADF and PP Unit Root Test Results

Variables	ADF Test t-statistic	Status	PP Test t-statistic	Status
<i>lnTR</i>	-6.108745***	I(1)	-18.23193***	I(1)
<i>lnINF</i>	-4.931731***	I(1)	-7.257942**	I(1)
<i>lnIR</i>	-6.954122***	I(1)	-7.048832***	I(1)
<i>lnEXR</i>	-7.779816***	I(1)	-7.794500***	I(1)
<i>lnRGDP</i>	-6.288055***	I(1)	-6.516299***	I(1)
<i>lnCAB</i>	-3.968834***	I(1)	-4.049544***	I(1)

Note. (***) indicate significant at 1%. All the variables are log linearized.

The results indicate that all variables are integrated into I(1), meaning they are non-stationary and show long-term trends. This implies that tax revenue performance in South Africa is affected by several macroeconomic factors that persistently influence its fluctuations. By examining the underlying dynamics of these variables, policymakers can improve their ability to predict and manage future tax revenue outcomes. This research highlights the importance of including long-term trends in tax revenue performance models to enhance their predictive accuracy.

Results Interpretation

In alignment with Agyemang-Badu et al. (2024), this study utilized two distinct regimes: one characterized by low volatility and the other by high volatility. Regime 1 signifies periods of economic growth or low volatility, while Regime 2 denotes recessions or crises associated with high volatility. MSM results are presented in Table 2.

In regime 1, the coefficient of inflation is -0.319524, while in regime 2, it is 0.035567. Both coefficients are insignificant, indicating that inflation does not significantly affect tax revenue. These results suggest that other factors may have a more substantial influence on tax revenue, overshadowing inflation's effects. Policymakers should consider these additional factors when making decisions regarding taxation and revenue generation.

The coefficient for interest rates in regime 1 is -7.982160, which is significant at the 5% level. In contrast, in regime 2, the coefficient is 0.344795 and is not statistically significant. These results suggest that during economic growth and stability (regime 1), changes in interest rates significantly impact tax revenue performance in South Africa. In recessions and crises (regime 2), interest rate effects on tax revenue performance are not statistically significant. This implies that during economic growth, the South African government can use changes in interest rates to influence tax revenue. Conversely, during recessions or crises, other factors may have a greater impact on tax revenue performance, making interest rate changes less effective at stimulating revenue growth. This highlights the importance of understanding different economic regimes and tailoring policy responses to manage tax revenue performance effectively.

Table 3. MSM Results

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistics	Prob.
Regime 1: low volatility				
C	136.9223	126.6250	1.081321	0.2796
INF	-0.319524	0.431203	-0.741007	0.4587
IR	-7.982160	3.508217	-2.275276	0.0229
EXR	0.180268	0.630094	0.286097	0.7748
RGDP	3.940239	1.466517	2.686801	0.0072
CAB	7.176762	1.850433	3.878424	0.0001
Regime 2: high volatility				
C	-7.638301	20.00059	-0.381904	0.7025
INF	0.035567	0.058228	0.610825	0.5413
IR	0.344795	0.615406	0.560272	0.5753
EXR	-0.009495	0.119537	-0.079428	0.9367
RGDP	3.087525	0.650268	4.748081	0.0000
CAB	-0.805281	0.335695	-2.398848	0.0164
Common				
LOG(SIGMA)	1.911993	0.083057	23.02024	0.0000
Transition Matrix Parameters				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistics	
P11-C	-1.103636	1.468483	-0.751548	0.4523
P21-C	-2.523294	0.848991	-2.972110	0.0030
Mean dependent var	10.07895	S.D. dependent var		12.03482
S.E. of regression	12.56115	Sum squared resid		12938.17
Durbin-Watson stat	2.517923	Log likelihood		-330.3028
Akaike info criterion	7.269532	Schwarz criterion		7.672776
Hannan-Quinn criter.	7.432473			

In regime 1, the exchange rate coefficient is 0.180268, while in regime 2, it is -0.009495. Both coefficients are insignificant, indicating that the exchange rate does not significantly affect tax revenue performance in South Africa. This suggests that fluctuations in the exchange rate between the South African Rand and other currencies do not have a substantial impact on tax revenue generation. Other macroeconomic factors may play a more important role in influencing tax revenue fluctuations in the country.

RGDP in regime 1 is 3.940239, significant at 1%. In comparison, regime 2 has a coefficient of 3.087525, also significant at the 1% level. These results demonstrate that economic growth positively affects tax revenue performance in South Africa, especially in regime 1, characterized by low volatility. During recessionary periods represented by regime 2, the positive impact of economic growth on tax revenue is slightly lower but remains significant. The findings suggest that the state of the economy is crucial in determining the effectiveness of tax revenue collection, emphasizing the importance for policymakers to consider macroeconomic factors when designing tax policies. Therefore, the government should focus on implementing measures that promote sustainable economic growth to enhance tax revenue performance.

The coefficient for the current account balance in regime 1 is 7.176762, significant at the 1% level. In contrast, regime 2 has a coefficient of -0.805281, significant at the 5% level. These findings indicate that a strong current account balance is associated with improved tax revenue performance during economic growth in regime 1. Conversely, in times of recession or crisis in regime 2, a negative current account balance is linked to a decrease in tax revenue. This highlights the importance of maintaining a healthy current account balance to support tax revenue generation in South Africa.

The analysis reveals that the LOG (SIGMA) is 1.911993, indicating a strong positive relationship with tax revenue performance. This suggests regime switching in the macroeconomic factors influencing tax revenue in South Africa. This result is statistically significant at the 1% level, emphasizing the impact of economic volatility on tax collection. Economic fluctuations can significantly affect the government's ability to generate tax revenue. Policymakers must consider economic volatility when designing fiscal policies to enhance tax collection.

This indicates that the transition from state 1 to state 2 significantly affects tax revenue in South Africa. The negative coefficient for P11-C shows that the influence of the first state on tax revenue is not statistically significant. In contrast, the significant coefficient for P21-C suggests that the second state has a strong and positive impact on tax revenue, at the 1% level of significance. Thus, we can conclude that the transition from the first state to the second state has a notable and positive effect on tax revenue in South Africa. This underscores that certain macroeconomic factors or conditions represented by the second state play a substantial role in generating tax revenue for the country.

The mean dependent variable of 10.07895 represents the average value in the model. The standard error of regression (S.E.) at 12.56115 indicates the accuracy of the model's estimates. The Durbin-Watson statistic of 2.517923 suggests potential autocorrelation in the model's residuals. The sum of squared residuals at 12938.17 reflects the model's overall fit to the data, with lower values indicating a better fit. The log likelihood of -

330.3028, along with the information criteria, provide additional measures of the model's goodness of fit and complexity. Together, these statistics assess the performance and reliability of the Markov-Switching Model in analyzing tax revenue dynamics in South Africa.

Wald Test

Wald tests determine whether regression coefficients differ significantly from zero. In analyzing tax revenue performance in South Africa, we use a Markov-switching model to explore the relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue. This model accounts for potential changes in these relationships over time, depending on the economic state. By applying the Wald test, we can assess the significance of these relationships, enhancing our understanding of tax revenue dynamics in South Africa.

Table 4. Wald Test.

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	10.39490	(6, 80)	0.0000
Chi-square	62.36939	6	0.0000

Macroeconomic factors and tax revenue performance in South Africa are significantly correlated based on statistical tests. The Wald Test F-statistic indicates that the model fits the data well, with a low probability of obtaining these results by chance. Additionally, the Chi-square test reinforces that macroeconomic factors strongly influence tax revenue performance in the country. These findings emphasize the importance of considering economic conditions when analyzing tax revenue trends in South Africa.

Probability Plot

The probability plot of the Markov-switching model illustrates the influence of varying economic conditions on South Africa's tax revenue performance. This analysis provides insights into how these conditions impact tax revenue generation, assisting in policy decisions and strategies to enhance tax collection and economic performance.

Figure 2. TR Smoothed Probabilities in the MSM-VAR model.

Figure 2 indicates a high probability (90.96%) that South Africa's tax revenue performance is in regime 2, while the probability of it being in regime 1 is much lower (9.04%). This suggests that macroeconomic factors affecting tax revenue in South Africa are more likely to be stable over time rather than experiencing sudden shifts. These findings offer insights for policymakers and analysts seeking to understand and predict tax revenue behavior in South Africa.

Figure 3. TR Filtered Probabilities in the MSM-VAR model.

Figure 3 shows that the average tax revenue in South Africa is likely to be in regime 2, with a probability of 0.901054. This suggests that tax revenue is relatively stable and less prone to sudden fluctuations. However, there is a small probability of 0.089496 that tax revenue could fall under regime 1, indicating a degree of uncertainty in the data.

Transition Probability

The possibility of changing from one regime or condition to another within a system or process is known as transition probability. Larger TR values, as shown in Table 5, indicate a greater chance of remaining in regime 2, as explained below.

Table 5. Transition Probability

South Africa	Regime 1	Regime 2
Regime 1	0.249059	0.750941
Regime 2	0.074241	0.925759
Durations	1.331663	13.46961

The results indicate that South Africa's tax revenue performance can be categorized into two states. State 1, with a probability of 0.249059, is marked by lower tax revenue levels. In contrast, State 2, with a probability of 0.750941, is associated with higher tax revenue levels. The expected durations for these states are approximately 1.33 quarters for State 1 and 13.47 quarters for State 2. This analysis highlights significant fluctuations in tax revenue performance in South Africa, with alternating periods of low and high revenue levels.

Discussion

A negative relationship exists between inflation and tax revenue in South Africa in regime one, although it is not statistically significant. This aligns with findings by Đurović et al. (2024) and Ayenew (2016), who identify a negative association between inflation and tax revenue in the Visegrad Group nations and Ethiopia, respectively. In contrast, regime two shows a positive relationship with tax revenue, which also remains statistically insignificant. These results align with studies by Imam and Jacobs (2014), Onakoya et al. (2020), and Desta et al. (2022), which found that inflation positively impacts tax income in 12 Middle Eastern countries, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Ethiopia, respectively. Overall, these findings suggest that inflation may affect tax revenue differently depending on the economic regime in South Africa. This supports the hypothesis that inflation has a regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance and implies that policymakers should consider specific economic conditions and the potential effects of inflation when designing fiscal policies.

There is a significant negative relationship between interest rates and tax revenue in regime one in South Africa. These results align with those found by Onakoya et al. (2020), which showed a negative correlation between interest rates and tax revenue in Sub-Saharan Africa. Conversely, in regime two, the relationship is positive but not statistically significant. These findings correspond to Basheer et al. (2019) and Gokpinar (2023), who identified a positive link between interest rates and tax revenue in Middle Eastern countries and Türkiye, respectively. Interest rates in South Africa affect tax revenue differently depending on the economic regime. In regime one, higher interest rates may decrease tax revenue, while in regime two, they could have a positive or neutral effect. Understanding how interest rates interact with tax revenue across different economic regimes is essential for policymakers to make informed decisions. This supports the hypothesis that interest rates have a regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance in South Africa, suggesting that the relationship between interest rates and tax revenue is not linear and can vary depending on the economic context.

The first regime shows a positive relationship between exchange rates and tax revenue in South Africa, consistent with Gaalya's (2015) findings in Uganda. In contrast, the second regime shows a negative relationship, aligning with Rutto's (2020) research, which found a negative correlation between exchange rates and tax revenue collection in Kenya. The contrast between these results suggests that exchange rates may have a different impact on tax revenue depending on South Africa's economic conditions. Therefore, policymakers must consider the specific economic context when formulating tax policies related to exchange rates. Understanding the factors influencing this relationship can lead to more effective policy decisions and enhance overall revenue collection. This supports the hypothesis that exchange rates have a regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance and highlights the importance of flexibility in tax policy decisions.

There is a significant positive relationship between RGDP growth and tax revenue in South Africa across both regimes, more pronounced in regime one. This finding aligns with Mardan and Stimmelmayer (2020), which identified a positive correlation between GDP and tax revenue in advanced economies. As the South African economy grows, tax

revenue tends to increase, indicating a strong connection between economic performance and tax collection. This insight is crucial for policymakers, as it underscores the importance of promoting economic growth to enhance tax revenue and improve fiscal sustainability. Additionally, the results support existing literature, reinforcing the idea that a thriving economy is essential for a robust tax system. This contradicts the hypothesis that RGDP growth has a regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance, suggesting a consistent pattern regardless of specific economic conditions.

The current account balance of South Africa has a positive and significant impact on tax revenue performance in the first regime. These results align with Abiad et al. (2009), who found significant relationships between current account balances and fiscal variables, and Gobachew et al. (2018), who found that exports and imports to GDP positively affect tax revenue in Ethiopia. The second regime reveals a negative impact, indicating that economic conditions affect the relationship between the current account balance and tax revenue. The positive relationship in the first regime suggests a stronger link during economic growth, likely due to increased trade activity and higher levels of economic output, resulting in more taxable income. Conversely, the negative relationship in the second regime may stem from economic downturns that disrupt trade and reduce tax revenue collection. Overall, these findings emphasize the importance of considering economic conditions when analyzing the current account balance and tax revenue. This supports the hypothesis that current account balances have a regime-dependent impact on tax revenue performance in a country's economy.

Conclusion

This study analyzed the macroeconomic factors influencing tax revenue performance in South Africa from 2000Q1 to 2023Q3. To determine whether changes in macroeconomic factors significantly impact tax revenue performance and how these effects differ between periods of economic expansion (regime 1) and recession (regime 2), the study applied the Markov Switching Model. The results revealed that in regime 1, the coefficient of inflation is negative and insignificant, while in regime 2, it is positive but also insignificant, indicating that inflation levels do not significantly impact tax revenue generation. This suggests that other factors may have a more substantial influence on tax revenue, overshadowing the effects of inflation, confirming a regime-dependent influence of inflation on tax revenue performance. The study further shows that interest rate changes negatively and significantly impact tax revenue performance during economic growth (regime 1) but positively and insignificantly during recessions (regime 2). This indicates that during economic growth, tax revenue is more sensitive to interest rate changes, potentially affecting the government's revenue generation. However, during recessions, the impact of interest rate changes on tax revenue is less pronounced, suggesting that other factors may play a more significant role. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for policymakers to make informed decisions about tax policy and economic management, confirming a regime-dependent influence of interest rates on tax revenue performance. The exchange rate coefficients in regime 1 are positive, while in regime 2, they are negative and both insignificant, suggesting no significant relationship between the exchange rate coefficients and the variables being studied. This may indicate that other factors are driving changes in the exchange rate, apart from the variables included in the analysis, confirming a regime-dependent influence of the exchange rate

on tax revenue performance. The study indicates that RGDP growth positively and significantly impacts tax revenue performance, particularly in regime 1 during economic growth; however, during recessions, the positive impact is slightly lower. This highlights the importance of a stable economy for sustaining tax revenue growth. The results suggest that policymakers should prioritize economic growth to boost tax revenue collection and implement measures to mitigate the adverse impacts of economic downturns, contradicting the hypothesis of a regime-dependent influence of RGDP growth on tax revenue performance. The current account balance in regime 1 is positive and significantly higher during economic growth, while in regime 2, it is negative and significant during recessions, indicating a pattern of fluctuation based on the economic conditions of each regime. This suggests that regime 1 benefits from stronger export performance and foreign investment inflows, leading to a surplus in the current account, while regime 2 may struggle with trade deficits and capital outflows, resulting in a negative current account balance, confirming a regime-dependent influence of the current account balance on tax revenue performance. Overall, the results show strong evidence of regime-dependent effects of macroeconomic factors on tax revenue performance in South Africa.

Original contribution

To the best of the author's knowledge, this is the first study to investigate the impact of macroeconomic factors on tax revenue performance using a Markov-Switching Model. This approach provides valuable insights into the complex relationship between macroeconomic factors and tax revenue performance, highlighting the importance of considering economic volatility in fiscal policy decision-making. By incorporating regime-switching dynamics into the analysis, this study offers a more nuanced understanding of the factors influencing tax collection in South Africa. These findings have significant implications for policymakers seeking to improve revenue generation and ensure fiscal sustainability amid economic uncertainty.

Policy recommendation

The study recommends a dynamic tax policy framework that adapts to macroeconomic conditions by modifying tax collection strategies during economic fluctuations. It recommends implementing counter-cyclical fiscal policies, such as maintaining higher tax revenue reserves during economic growth, to buffer against revenue declines during downturns. Additionally, tax policies should alleviate the negative impacts of inflation and interest rates on tax compliance and revenue collection. The text emphasizes the importance of aligning tax policy with trade and currency strategies, improving trade facilitation, and supporting export-oriented sectors. It advocates prioritizing policies that promote sustained economic growth and diversifying revenue streams to reduce dependence on volatile sources.

Limitations

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of this study. Due to the use of historical data, the analysis may not fully reflect the complex and dynamic nature of the economy. Furthermore, other unconsidered factors could also affect tax revenue performance.

Additional research and analysis are needed to better understand these limitations and refine tax policies accordingly.

Areas of Future Research

Future studies should explore how performance in key economic sectors (e.g., mining, manufacturing, services) affects tax revenue under varying economic conditions and regimes. Utilizing advanced models, such as machine learning algorithms, will enable policymakers to make informed decisions that promote economic growth and stability. These studies are essential for developing South Africa's tax policy and ensuring long-term financial sustainability. Additionally, they can help devise strategies to mitigate revenue fluctuations. By integrating various factors and employing data analysis techniques, a robust and adaptive tax system can be established. It is also important to investigate the role of taxpayer behavior, including trust in government and the perceived fairness of the tax system, in shaping compliance and its impact on revenue collection.

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